

Studies on 4-Thiazolidinone. Part-VI. Synthesis and Anti-microbial Activity of 5-(2',4'-Dichlorophenoxy-methyl)-2-(2'-aryl-5'(H)-4'-thiazolidinone)-1,3,4-thiadiazole

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Some new 4-thiazolidinone derivatives bearing 1,3,4-thiadiazole moiety have been synthesised by treating thiosemicarbazide with 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid in presence of phosphorous oxychloride. This on treatment with aromatic aldehydes gave Schiff bases of thiadiazoles which on further reaction with thioglycolic, thiolactic and thiomalic acids, yielded the desired products. The structures of the compounds have been established by elemental analyses and spectral study. The compounds have been evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against different microorganisms.

4-Thiazolidinone derivatives are endowed with broad spectrum of biological activities¹. Thiosemicarbazides are reported to possess good antibacterial, antifungal and herbicidal activities². 2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid is also a selective weed killer³. In view of the interesting activities, we have synthesised some 4-thiazolidinone derivatives.

Thiosemicarbazide was condensed with 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid and phosphorous oxychloride to get 2-amino-5-(2',4'-dichlorophenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1). Compound 1 on treatment with aromatic aldehydes gave Schiff bases of thiadiazole (2). The latter on condensation with thio glycolic, thiolactic and thiomalic acids yielded the substituted-4-thiazolidinones (3-5).

The 4-thiazolidinone derivatives were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*, and fungal strains *Aspergillus niger* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* at the concentration of 50 µg ml⁻¹ using DMF as solvent by the cup-plate method⁴.

The results obtained from antimicrobial activity showed that most of the compounds were moderately active against different strains of bacteria and fungi as compared to standard antibiotics. The most active compounds (3) were those bearing Ar = 4-chlorophenyl, 2-furfuryl against *S. aureus* (zone of inhibition 17-18 mm) and Ar = phenyl-3,5-dichloro-2-hydroxyphenyl against *S. pyogenes* (18-20 mm), 2-chlorophenyl and 2-furfuryl against *E. coli* (19-20 mm), and Ar = 2-chlorophenyl and 4-hydroxyphenyl against *A. niger* (22-24 mm).

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 435

X = H (3a-t)
X = CH₃ (4a-t)
X = CH₂COOH (5a-t)

Scheme 1

spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Hitachi R-1200 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

2-Amino-5-(2',4'-dichlorophenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1): A mixture of 2,4-dichloroacetic acid (0.01 mol), thiosemicarbazide (0.012 mol) and

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.*	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %
3a	Phenyl	190	80
b	2-Hydroxyphenyl	220	73
c	4-Hydroxyphenyl	205	70
d	3-Hydroxyphenyl	230	65
e	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	210	50
f	3-Aminophenyl	270	78
g	4-Aminophenyl	242	82
h	2-Anisyl	140	75
i	4-Anisyl	126	80
j	2-Chlorophenyl	174	70
k	4-Chlorophenyl	178	75
l	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	210	69
m	3,5-Dichloro-2-hydroxyphenyl	180	60
n	Cinnamyl	280	72
o	2-Furfuryl	187	69
p	2-Nitrophenyl	212	54
q	3-Nitrophenyl	235	50
r	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	182	62
s	3,4-Dimethylaminophenyl	190	65
t	2,4-Dimethylaminophenyl	171	72
4a	Phenyl	174	65
b	2-Hydroxyphenyl	193	72
c	4-Hydroxyphenyl	185	68
d	3-Hydroxyphenyl	205	70
e	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	215	62
f	3-Aminophenyl	175	61
g	4-Aminophenyl	195	72
h	2-Anisyl	155	70
i	4-Anisyl	170	75
j	2-Chlorophenyl	160	60
k	4-Chlorophenyl	172	65
l	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	205	70
m	3,5-Dichloro-2 hydroxyphenyl	190	60
n	Cinnamyl	220	69
o	2-Furfuryl	185	72
p	2-Nitrophenyl	215	54
q	3-Nitrophenyl	230	58
r	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	180	60
s	3,4-Dimethylaminophenyl	192	65
t	2,4-Dimethylaminophenyl	175	72
5a	Phenyl	220	69
b	2-Hydroxyphenyl	230	70
c	4-Hydroxyphenyl	210	74
d	3-Hydroxyphenyl	250	67
e	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	205	55
f	3 Aminophenyl	195	65
g	4-Aminophenyl	185	69
h	2-Anisyl	155	73
i	4-Anisyl	165	76
j	2-Chlorophenyl	178	65
k	4-Chlorophenyl	180	65
l	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	220	60
m	3,5-Dichloro-2-hydroxyphenyl	190	70
n	Cinnamyl	242	64
o	2-Furfuryl	169	58
p	2 Nitrophenyl	235	62
q	3-Nitrophenyl	248	71
r	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	192	74
s	3,4-Dimethylaminophenyl	198	66
t	2,4-Dimethylaminophenyl	173	67

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**For 3a-t, X=H; 4a-t, X=CH₃; 5a-t, X=CH₂COOH.

phosphorous oxychloride (0.012 mol) was warmed at 60° for 1 h and temperature was raised to 90–95° for an additional 1.5 h. The contents were then poured on to crushed ice, cooled to 10°, the pH adjusted to 9–10 with 10 M NaOH, and the resulting solid was crystallised from dioxane-DMF (3:1) solvent, (70–75%), m.p. 220° (Found: C, 44.12; H, 2.81; N, 17.12. C₉H₇ON₃Cl₂ requires: C, 44.18; H, 2.86; N, 17.18%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 450 (pri N–H sym), 1 645 (C=N), 600 (C–S–C thiadiazole moiety), 1 050 (N–N), 3 100–3 050 (Ar C–H) and 2 870 cm⁻¹ (alkane CH₂). Similarly other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

5-(2',4'-Dichlorophenoxyethyl)-2-substituted-benzalamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (2): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), ethanol (95%; 30 ml) and benzaldehyde (0.02 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath at 90° for 6 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from DMF, m.p. 200° (Found: C, 57.71; H, 3.28; N, 12.58. C₁₆H₁₁ON₃Cl₂ requires: C, 57.75; H, 3.31; N, 12.63%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 645 (–N=CH thiadiazole moiety), 600 (C–S–C), 1 050 (N–N), 3 100–3 050 cm⁻¹ (Ar C–H); δ 7.4–7.9 (5H, m, ArH), 5.52 (2H, s, O–CH₂). Similarly other Schiff bases were prepared (Table 1).

5-(2',4'-Dichlorophenoxyethyl)-2-(2'-aryl-5'(H)-4'-thiazolidinone)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (3a): Compound 2 (0.01 mol) was heated with thioglycolic acid (0.012 mol) in an oil-bath at 115–20° for 12–15 h. The resulting product was isolated using sodium bicarbonate and crystallised from DMF, (60–65%), m.p. 160° (Found: C, 49.00; H, 2.82; N, 9.48. C₁₈H₁₃O₂N₃S₂Cl₂ requires: C, 49.26; H, 2.96; N, 9.57%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 715 (C=O), 690 (C–S–C) and 3 100–3 050 (Ar C–H); δ 7.4–7.9 (5H, m, ArH), 5.52 (2H, s, O–CH₂), 3.40 (2H, s, CH₂). Similarly other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

5-(2',4'-Dichlorophenoxyethyl)-2-(2'-aryl-5'-methyl-4'-thiazolidinone)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (4a): Compound 2 (0.01 mol) was heated with thiolactic acid (0.01 mol) in an oil-bath at 115–20° for 12–14 h. The resulting product was isolated using sodium bicarbonate and crystallised from DMF, (60–62%), m.p. 180° (Found: C, 50.35; H, 3.10; N, 9.25. C₁₉H₁₅O₂N₃S₂Cl₂ requires: C, 50.39; H, 3.30; N, 9.28%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 750 (C=O), 690 (C–S–C) and 3 100–3 050 (Ar C–H); δ 7.4–7.9 (5H, m, ArH), 3.94 (1H, q, S–CHR), 1.5 (3H, d, CH₃) and 5.52 (2H, s, O–CH₂). Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

5-(2',4'-Dichlorophenoxyethyl)-2-(2'-aryl-5'-carboxymethyl-4'-thiazolidinone)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (5a): Compound 2 (0.01 mol) was heated with thiomalic acid (0.015 mol) at 160° for 2 h and then raised at 180° for 1 h in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride. The resulting solid was purified, (50–55%), m.p. 280° (Found: C, 48.34; H, 3.00; N, 8.46. C₂₀H₁₅O₄N₃S₂Cl₂ requires: C, 48.38; H, 3.02; N, 8.49%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 750 (C=O), 690 (C–S–C) and 3 100–3 050 (Ar C–H); δ 7.4–7.9 (5H, m, ArH), 5.52 (2H, s, O–CH₂), 3.94 (1H, q, S–CHR') and 2.6 (2H, d,

CH₂COOH). Similarly other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

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